

PATHS IN INTERACTIVE SOUND VISUALIZATION: FROM *AVOL* TO *AV CLASH*

Nuno N. Correia

Aalto University,
School of Arts, Design and Architecture,
Media Lab Helsinki
mail@nunocorreia.com

ABSTRACT

This paper compares two multimodal net art projects, *AVOL* and *AV Clash*, by the author and André Carrilho (under the name Video Jack). Their objective is to create projects enabling integrated audiovisual expression that are flexible, easy to use, playful and engaging to experience. The projects are contextualized with related works. The methodology for the research is presented, with an emphasis on experience-focused Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) perspectives. The comparative evaluation of the projects focuses on the analysis of the answers to an online questionnaire. *AVOL* and *AV Clash* have adopted an Interactive AudioVisual Objects (IAVO) approach, which is a major contribution from these projects, consisting of the integration of sound, audio visualization and Graphical User Interface (GUI). Strengths and weaknesses detected in the projects are analysed. Generic conclusions are discussed, mainly regarding simplicity and harmony versus complexity and serendipity in audiovisual projects. Finally, paths for future development are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

AV Clash (<http://www.avclash.com>) is a multimodal online project that allows for the integrated playback and manipulation of sound and visuals [1]. It was developed by the author and André Carrilho (assisted by Gokce Taskan), under the collective name Video Jack, and released in 2010. The sounds are retrieved from *Free-sound.org* (<http://www.freesound.org>), an online sound database. *AV Clash* is the latest in a series of projects that aim to answer the following research question: how to develop a flexible, playful, engaging and easy to use tool for audiovisual expression. In this series of projects, *AV Clash* is particularly related to *AVOL* (AudioVisual On-Line)—it can be considered an evolution of this earlier project (from 2007). Video Jack's previous projects had been mostly presented in performances and exhibitions. With *AVOL* and *AV Clash*, Video Jack intended to reach a broader audience by additionally using the Internet as a platform, moving into the territory of net art. The projects also challenge the boundaries between author, audience and user. With these projects, Video Jack aim to pass to their audience part of the authorial process.

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The projects fit into a broader cultural context of audience interest in participatory engagement with music; the ascendance of the music video with the emergence of MTV in the 1980s ([2], p. 31); and increasing importance of Internet as a distribution channel for media, particularly music and music videos. The interest in participatory engagement can be exemplified by the popularity of music games such as the *Guitar Hero* series, the third most influential game of the past decade according to *Wired* magazine [3]. As demonstration of the increasing importance of the Internet as music distribution channel, more than 660 million digital songs were sold in the first semester of 2011 in the USA, an 11 percent increase from the first half of 2010 [4]. The Internet has also become "a superb music video resource", contrasting with the mutation of MTV and other music video channels into "a celebration of celebrity and wealth" ([2], p. viii).

2. FROM AVOL TO AV CLASH

Figure 1. Screenshot of AVOL

Figure 2. Detail of IAVO in AVOL

AVOL (<http://www.videojackstudios.com/avol>) allows for the manipulation of audio and visuals aggregated in seven Interactive AudioVisual Objects (IAVOs) incorporating a Graphical User Interface (GUI), each with playback control functionalities including four main content options (Figures 1, 2). Each IAVO represents a certain type of sound (for example, drums or guitar).

The audio component in *AVOL* is fixed—it consists of music loops composed by the author, all with the same length. These loops were composed taking into account that they would be interchangeable. An internal clock ensures that the sounds remain synchronized. These elements contribute to a more traditional "musical" character of *AVOL*, compared to the more chaotic nature of *AV Clash* (where sounds have different duration and diverse styles). *AVOL* possesses basic playback functionality (including stop and solo for each IAVO) and few audio manipulation options—only volume can be controlled.

The visuals in *AVOL* and *AV Clash* share multiple common characteristics: they consist of audio-reactive concentric vector animations (28 in *AVOL*, four per IAVO; 96 in *AV Clash*); the audio reactivity is based on the scaling of animations according to the amplitude of the correspondent sound; and the animations in both projects are abstract, conceived as a subjective interpretation of the type of sound they were meant to represent. Audio reactive visuals are an important element in both projects—they allow for the multimodal illusion that Chion has named "synchresis": "the forging of an immediate and necessary relationship between something one sees and something one hears at the same time" ([5], p. 224).

With *AV Clash*, the author intended to solve some of the weaknesses he detected in *AVOL*: scarce amount of sounds; inexistent sound customization; insufficient audio manipulation; limited playfulness; lack of randomization features; and usability deficiencies. *AV Clash* addressed those limitations, while maintaining the IAVO approach of integrating GUI with sound visualization (although the number of objects was reduced to four) and the style of visuals (Figures 3, 4).

Figure 3. Screenshot of AV Clash

Figure 4. Detail of IAVO in AV Clash

The limitations related to the amount and customization of sounds were addressed by connecting to the online sound database *Freesound.org*, which classifies sounds by tag. *AV Clash* accesses 11 of the tags (such as "noise" and "voice") with the highest number of sounds and retrieves the most popular sounds (according to number of downloads) within those tags. Initially 20 sounds per tag were taken into account, resulting in a total of approximately 220 sounds.

By accessing a menu system, users can change the sounds and animations contained in each object, and even the tag of that object. Four easily accessible pairings of sounds and visuals ("favourites") can be picked for each of the objects (these four pairings are randomized at the start of each session). An additional tag ("avclash") was set up in order to allow users to upload their sounds to *AV Clash*, via *Freesound.org*.

Sound manipulation capabilities were added: effects ("echo" and "filter") and sound trimming (start and end points). As an extra element of playfulness, users can "throw" objects around the screen. A randomization feature was created: a "shuffle" button that randomizes which sound and animation are playing in each object, and moves the object in a random direction, thus enabling a quick change of audiovisual character with a single button press. Another issue addressed in *AV Clash* was usability. The author felt that the lack of identification of each object in *AVOL* hindered its ease of use. In *AV Clash*, objects are identified by colour and by a balloon-shaped "info tip" showcasing the tag name. Moving the cursor over a GUI element reveals further information.

3. CONTEXTUALIZATION WITH RELATED WORKS

There is a long history behind the combination of music with the visual arts, and the pursuit of a correspondence between image and sound. Ancient Greek philosophers such as Plato and Aristotle speculated that there was a correlation "between the musical scale and the rainbow spectrum of hues" [6]. In the 19th century, Richard Wagner envisioned a genre of artwork that would combine different arts—a "total art work" (*gesamtkunstwerk*). Wagner described it as an operatic performance that encompasses music, theatre and the visual arts: "the true Drama is only conceivable as proceeding from a common urge of every art towards the most direct appeal to a

common public". To achieve this, "each separate branch of art can only be fully attained by the reciprocal agreement and co-operation of all the branches in their common message" ([7], p. 5).

The development of cinema opened the door to further explorations between music and image. Oskar Fischinger (1900-1967) was one of the notable pioneers of this field and was dedicated to a purely abstract approach of visual representation of music. Fischinger was inspired by Bernhard Diebold, who called for "a new blend of the fine arts, music, dance and cinema—or better, new artists, 'Bildmusikers' [visual musicians]" to achieve Wagner's ideal of *gesamtkunstwerk*, "preferably abstract in nature" ([8], p. 4). When Fischinger moved to the USA in 1936, "his work and presence became an inspiration to a second generation of Colour-Music artists" such as Jordan Belson, Harry Smith and brothers John and James Whitney, who decided to take up abstract animation influenced by him [9].

The development of computing brought about new possibilities for artists in visual music. John Whitney was among the first to explore these possibilities, and his elegant abstract work was an inspiration for the animations in *AVOL* and *AV Clash*. Golan Levin is a notable example of a contemporary artist in this field, with projects such as his *Audiovisual Environment Suite (AVES)*, "an interactive software that allows for the creation and manipulation of simultaneous visuals and sound in real time" ([10], p. 133), using an abstract aesthetics. Levin's influence is apparent in the work of Video Jack, as is Toshio Iwai's, with works such as *Electroplankton*, a set of ten "musical toys", each taking place "in some sort of bizarre petri dish—or perhaps a very musical aquarium—filled with different species of plankton that can produce sound and light when you interact with them" [11].

4. METHODOLOGY AND FRAMEWORK

Between April and May 2011, an online questionnaire was conducted to determine if *AV Clash* had succeeded in its objectives, as defined by the research question it addresses: how to create a tool for integrated audiovisual creativity, with customizable content, that is flexible, easy to use, playful and engaging to observe? Because some of the objectives are related to solving insufficiencies detected in previous projects, the questionnaire included sections comparing *AV Clash* to earlier projects by Video Jack: *Master and Margarita* and *AVOL*. *Master and Margarita*, a project that shares fewer resemblances with *AV Clash* than *AVOL* does, will be left out of the scope of this paper.

The different elements of the research question *AV Clash* addresses structured the sections of the questionnaire: 1) audiovisual integration and type of content; 2) amount of content; 3) flexibility—content manipulation capabilities; 4) usability, ease of use and exploration; 5) creativity and experience. Each section included questions comparing *AV Clash* with previous projects. The questionnaire was composed of 81 questions, mostly

close-ended, but also 13 open-ended ones.¹ For this article, the comparison questions and the questions related to future developments are taken into account.

In order to develop the different sections of the questionnaire, literature on experience-focused human-computer interaction (HCI) and usability were important sources. Experience-focused literature has detected gaps between HCI methodologies and the ones used by new media artists. On the one hand, some authors identify a tendency in interactive art to ignore HCI methodologies for interaction, "based on a mostly unstated belief that they do not measure aspects of interactive artworks that are of interest to artists" ([12], p. 241). Höök et al. consider that user studies can assist artists "that want to express themselves through an interactive system" to make the interaction "work as intended" ([12], p. 248). On the other hand, some authors note that evaluation of experience-focused applications should go beyond usability: "to evaluate merely on usability is to miss the very point of these technologies" ([13], p. 2118).

As a consequence, the field of HCI has been developing the concept of experience-focused HCI, "recognizing a widening of the sphere of HCI out of the workplace and into the world, and emphasizing the importance of culture, emotion, and lived experience" ([13], p. 2118). Following in this direction, Peterson et al. propose the notion of aesthetic interaction as an "extended expressiveness towards interactive systems", that would reach "beyond ideals of efficiency and transparency, e.g. like considering the emotions, attraction, and affect invoked by design" ([14], p. 269). It is focused on "intriguing and sometimes even ambiguous aspects", and it aims to "encourage the user to explore and playfully appropriate the system", by "creating involvement, experience, surprise and serendipity in interaction" ([14], p. 274). Explorability was indeed an important aim in the design of the projects, since, as Donald Norman states, "one important method of making systems easier to learn and use is to make them explorable, to encourage the user to experiment and learn the possibilities through active exploration" ([15], p. 183).

5. RESULTS

The questionnaire was promoted in the Video Jack home page and related sites. It was open to any respondents, and was answered by 22 anonymous test users. Approximately two thirds of the respondents had a master's degree. The vast majority (91%) of these test users had experience as new media artist and/or new media designer. Half had experience as DJ (disk jockey) and/or musician. All had experience as viewers/listeners of new media art projects and of net art projects. Therefore, the respondents appear to be experienced users of interactive content and familiar with media production. On average, the respondents have used *AV Clash* two times and spent 12 minutes playing with the project per session.

¹ A static version of the questionnaire can be found at: http://www.videojackstudios.com/survey/avclash_questionnaire.pdf

5.1 Audiovisual Integration and Type of Content

AV Clash is considered to integrate audio and visuals better by approximately half of the respondents, while nearly one-fourth answered *AVOL*, and an equal percentage of users consider them to be in the same level. From the six test users who preferred *AVOL*, four mention the issue of simplicity, with one user elaborating further: "the connection with the sound is more simple and more obvious". Two of these test users replied that the end result was more appealing. From the respondents who expressed preference in the sound and image integration in *AV Clash*, three answered that the project, in terms of interface and logic, was easier to understand. Two of the respondents mentioned that their choice was due to a higher amount of manipulation options in *AV Clash*.

The results are slightly more balanced when comparing exclusively the sonic approach of *AV Clash* with the one in *AVOL*. 41% of the test users prefer the sound and music approach of *AV Clash*, against 32% who prefer the approach of *AVOL*, with 27% enjoying equally both. The test users who preferred the sounds in *AVOL* stated that the synchronization of the loops, the fact that the sounds were curated, and the inclusion of percussive elements were factors for their choice. Three test users who preferred *AV Clash* mentioned the variety of sounds (and another one mentioned the lack of this variety in *AVOL*), while two mentioned the higher level of control as reasons for their preference. Another respondent preferred the sounds in *AV Clash* because they were "more abstract and neutral". One of the users who enjoyed equally both mentioned that while *AVOL* offers more harmony due to its pre-selected set, *AV Clash* offers more variety. Another respondent who also manifested equal preference mentioned that *AVOL* was better for rhythm due to loop synchronization, while for other type of sounds *AV Clash* was preferable due to its larger amount of content. One user preferred *AVOL* due to the larger number of control possibilities, which reveals there were aspects of *AV Clash* that remained undiscovered (since it is the latter that offers more control functionalities).

5.2 Amount of Content

Figure 5. Appeal of additional content in AV Clash

One of the main aims of *AV Clash* was to increase substantially the number of sounds that could be accessed, compared to *AVOL*. One of the sections of questionnaire concentrated on this aspect. Approximately two thirds

(68%) of the respondents consider that the possibility of accessing a larger amount of content in *AV Clash* than in the previous project is appealing, against 27% who do not (Figure 5).

In *AV Clash*, most of the content is not immediately accessible or visible (only 16 sounds and animations are). To access the extra content, users have to press a "settings" button. More experienced users are assumed to discover this additional content, and value it more, while novice users may be less likely to do so. Following the conclusions of Kiefer et al., who state that allotted practice time is particularly important in a musical usability study ([16], p. 89), the duration of the interaction with the system (measured by the number of interaction sessions) was correlated with the appeal of additional content. Even though correlation analysis did not reveal any substantial relationship between both, a graphic comparing number of interaction settings with the appeal of additional content reveals that users who have interacted more with *AV Clash* tend to find the additional content very appealing, with a more varied range of responses for those who have interacted less (Figure 6). This leads to the conclusion that the diversity of content in *AV Clash* may remain undiscovered for novice users.

Figure 6. Comparing appeal of additional content (y axis) with number of interaction sessions (x axis)

5.3 Flexibility, Usability and Intuitiveness

Figure 7. Appeal of additional audio manipulation in AV Clash

Besides increasing the amount of content compared to *AVOL*, *AV Clash* also aimed to increase the amount of sound manipulation capabilities, such as "echo" and "filter" audio effects and sound trimming. A section of the

questionnaire was dedicated to assessing if the test users valued these developments. Comparing *AV Clash* to *AVOL*, approximately half of the test users consider the additional audio manipulation options in the former to be interesting, against 18% who did not. Nearly one quarter of the respondents are indifferent (Figure 7).

Approximately three quarters of the test users have spent more time interacting with *AV Clash* than with *AVOL*. When asked about the reason for this preference, in a multiple-choice question, 73% of the respondents mentioned the larger amount of manipulation options, while 40% mentioned the larger amount of content. 47% of the users indicated "other", and these were asked to elaborate. One of the users stated that "the interface felt clearer, and easier to learn and manipulate". To assess if more time spent interacting with *AV Clash* would lead to a higher interest in audio manipulation options, the number of interaction sessions were compared with the appeal of the added functionalities (regarding *AVOL*). Unlike the added audio content, appreciation for the extra audio manipulation options does not seem to increase with more interaction sessions (Figure 8). One possible explanation is that most of the audio manipulation options are immediately available (simply by dragging faders on the IAVOs), unlike most of the added content, which requires further exploration (accessing the settings area).

Figure 8. Comparing appeal of additional manipulation options (y axis) with number of interaction sessions (x axis)

The additional options in *AV Clash*, compared to *AVOL*, created a challenge: how to add functionalities to *AVOL* while improving the usability? A section of the questionnaire compared the ease of use of *AVOL* and *AV Clash*. The answers are evenly split. Approximately one third of users consider *AV Clash* to be more intuitive to use, whereas a similar percentage reply that *AVOL* is more intuitive. More than one-fourth of respondents consider that they are on the same level regarding intuitiveness. When asked the reasons behind their choices, six out of the eight users who considered *AVOL* more intuitive mention the simpler interface and fewer options as the reasons for their choice. Three of the users who found *AV Clash* more intuitive manifested preference in the project's UI.

5.4 Creativity and Experience

All the previous aspects—multisensoriality, type and amount of content, manipulation options, ease of use—aim to contribute to engagement, playfulness and expressiveness. Particularly important was to evaluate the degree of expression allowed by *AV Clash*: did the new features added to *AV Clash* contribute to a more creative experience than *AVOL*, as it aimed to?

As previously mentioned, nearly three quarters of the users have spent more time interacting with *AV Clash* than with *AVOL*. More than half (59%) of the respondents consider that *AV Clash* gives a higher feeling of creativity, whereas two respondents chose *AVOL*. Around one quarter answer both, and two test users answered that they do not get a feeling of creativity from either. Of the 13 respondents who consider that *AV Clash* gives a greater feeling of creativity than *AVOL*, seven mention more control or more options and one respondent mentions more variety in sound as reasons for their choice. One of the respondents who consider that both projects give the same feeling of creativity considers that both projects shape the sound and visuals too much to allow for their own creativity, and one of the users who did not get a feeling of creativity from either mentions that the projects are "too structured". One of the two test users who consider *AVOL* to offer a more creative experience mentions that the selected sounds "fit together nicely", adding that switching between them created interesting results.

5.5 Future Developments

The final section of the questionnaire was dedicated to exploring possible future developments of *AV Clash*. Test users were questioned regarding what functionalities they found attractive to be added to the project, by selecting from a list or writing their own suggestions.

Regarding suggestions for new functionalities, recording audio/video or saving options (chosen by 64% of the respondents) and sharing recordings by e-mail or social networks (selected by 73% of the users) are among the most desired additions. Visual customization (drawing or uploading visuals) is important for 73% of the respondents, whereas sound input is relevant for 59% of the test users. The lower diversity of visuals in *AV Clash* compared with the diversity of sounds can explain a stronger wish for visual customization. Concerning other platforms for using *AV Clash*, 64% of the respondents would like to use it as installation, whereas approximately half would wish to see *AV Clash* adapted to other devices, such as games consoles or mobile phones. Collaborative functionalities would also be important for approximately half of the respondents. Users seem to be less interested in increased manipulation capabilities (46% consider it important), higher diversity of content (only 19% consider useful to add more tags to the 12 existing ones) and more random functionalities (one third regard this as an important aspect).

When asked to freely suggest future developments for *AV Clash*, three of the respondents suggested usability improvements, such as: better indication of what areas

can be clicked on; increasing the size of the buttons; adding more explanatory texts to interactive elements; adding keyboard shortcuts; and adding an "intro mode" with more explanations and tool tips. Five other test users suggested feature additions. Some of these additions coincided with the ones presented in the multiple answer questions, while others went beyond those, such as: using the spatial coordinates of the screen to affect some parameters; using physics when throwing; adding a sound synthesis engine with short midi patterns; and adding a master volume slider.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The answers to the questionnaire might be biased towards favouring *AV Clash*. As it was the most recent project, and the focus of most of the questions, respondents might have spent more time interacting with it than with *AVOL*. Additionally, the number of the respondents to the questionnaire was not high (22), limiting the extrapolation of results and the achievement of more generic conclusions. The length of the questionnaire (81 questions) might have intimidated other potential respondents. Despite this, the results offer insights to a wide range of important issues related to interactive audiovisual projects, and also point the way for future developments in this path. Taking into account experience-focused HCI perspectives in the evaluation of the projects, while considering usability issues, was important in order to cover a wide range of topics.

One of the most important contributions of the projects is the concept of Interactive Audiovisual Objects (IAVOs) as a modular approach to visual music projects: each sound is combined with a matching animation visualizing it, containing GUI elements. Those GUI elements are embedded in the visuals, and aesthetically integrated with the animation style and with the overall visual character of the project, adding to a coherent experience. The projects implement this IAVO approach differently, leading to important distinctions. The IAVOs in *AV Clash* contain a larger number of GUI elements than *AVOL*, which results in diverse levels of satisfaction for different types of users.

The results of the questionnaire show that *AV Clash* was more successful than *AVOL* in most of the aspects analysed: integration of sound and visuals; amount and diversity of content; flexibility of manipulation; creativity and experience. Some important exceptions arise, however. In terms of audio, comparing the chaotic and diverse approach of *AV Clash* with the more conventional and synchronized nature of the music loops in *AVOL* leads to nearly balanced results (41% prefer the former, and 32% the latter). Notably, *AV Clash* seems to have not succeeded in improving the usability of *AVOL*. When asked which one was easier to use, users were evenly split between the two projects. The improvements in usability that were introduced ("info tips", colour coding of IAVOs) seem to have been offset by the complexity of the added functionalities.

Although *AV Clash* was the most successful project for the majority of users, in most of the sections of the questionnaire, it is important to analyse why a still significant

minority of users preferred *AVOL*. As was presented above, *AVOL* obtained similar results to *AV Clash* in terms of ease of use. When asked for the reasons behind their answer, six out of the eight users who consider *AVOL* more intuitive mention the simpler interface and fewer options of the project. Four of the six users that prefer the connection of sound and visuals in *AVOL* favour its "simplicity", while two find the end result more appealing (presumably on the sonic side, as the visual side is aesthetically similar). The one third of respondents who prefer the sonic approach of *AVOL* appreciated the synchronization and harmony of sounds ("they fit together nicely", as one user put it) and rhythmical nature. A project with a limited set of options and simple interface, and with a harmonious, well-synchronized audiovisual content, can be as appealing as a more complex and diverse one. For some (although a minority according to this study), more content and more manipulation options do not lead to a higher engagement. Adding functionalities and content might be attractive for some users, but others prefer a simpler, more curated approach. *AVOL* and *AV Clash* represent a trade-off: simplicity of usage, synchronization and harmony of content in the former, versus diversity of options, variety and unpredictability of content in the latter, with users positioning themselves differently in their preferences.

There appear to be three groups of users: those who prefer the simpler and more "harmonious" approach of *AVOL*; those who are happier with the higher diversity and options of *AV Clash*; and one third group of users that feel that they are "too structured to allow for creativity", as one of the users expressed. Future interactive audiovisual applications (such as further developments of *AV Clash*) could contemplate this third group, by providing more customization options and more content (particularly on the visual side). The identification of these three groups, with different demands regarding content and functionalities, might be important in terms of targeting future interactive audiovisual projects.

Paths for future developments of *AV Clash* should contemplate wishes expressed by the respondents, and these might be relevant for other audiovisual projects. Recording audiovisual sessions and sharing these by email or social networks would be attractive features for, respectively, 63% and 73% of the users. This could be accomplished by adding a "sequencer" (editable or not) that would record all the steps taken by the user, retrievable with a custom URL, or simply by recording video or audio files, with the option of uploading them to sites such as *YouTube* or *SoundCloud*. Possibly due to the lower variety of the visuals compared with the audio in *AV Clash*, developments in visual customization would be important for 73% of the respondents. A solution for this could be the creation of a drawing area within the project that would generate vector animations, or the creation of a vector drawing and animation database, which would be an adequate counterpoint to the sound database provided by *Freesound.org*. Other platforms should also be explored for *AV Clash*, or similar future interactive audiovisual projects. Nearly two thirds of the respondents would like to use it as installation, and approximately half would enjoy using *AV Clash* in other platforms such as

games consoles or mobile devices. Multi-touch screen platforms such as iOS and Android devices seem to be particularly appropriate to the IAVO approach, as users would be manipulating the visualizations more directly with their fingers. Collaborative functionalities, allowing for networked composition for example, could also be added, as these are considered important for approximately half of the respondents.

However, care should be taken when adding new functionalities. Users seem to be less attracted to more manipulation options, or to adding content, than to improvements in ease of use. Usability problems seem to be quite relevant—it is an issue that often appears under the open-ended questions, even in the section related to future developments. These problems confirm the importance of user studies in art projects, as Höök et al. have advocated [12]. Improvements in the interaction design should encourage users to better "experiment and learn the possibilities through active exploration" ([15], p. 183). Future developments of *AV Clash*, and similar audiovisual projects, should particularly foster the explorability of content.

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